

Λ -TRIANGLE

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Another isosceles triangle (Λ) with the inner centrally symmetric square is described too. It could be seen as the golden ratio's cubic extension (λ).

As a possible sequel to an earlier work [1] here we will describe yet another no less interesting isosceles triangle. It also contains centrally inscribed square but now with one vertex touching none of its sides. The related picture looks like this bellow

The relation¹ between radius r of the circle and now diagonal d of the inscribed square (assuming $d=2$) reads as follows

$$r^2(r^2 - 1) = (r + 1)^2$$

and after some algebra

* [Wave Cosmodynamics](#)

$$(r + 1)(r^3 - r^2 - r - 1) = 0.$$

The above equation in general is quartic in degree. However, because one of its real roots is -1, and still accepting that as geometrically not intuitive, we finally get a basic cubic equation

$$r^3 - r^2 - r - 1 = 0$$

with one real solution

$$r = 1.8392867\dots$$

A possible interpretation of the equation as well as the number itself might be to recognize all that as an cubic extension of the second order “golden section” equation [2][3]. In a sense, and in an analogy to the well known φ , the above number might be seen as a novel constant λ . Moreover, the Λ -triangle itself could also be recognized as a natural geometric representation of λ .

Based on the above now we are able to calculate the apex angle of the Λ -triangle, i.e.

$$\alpha = 2\arctan(1/1.8392867) \approx 57.06488^\circ$$

In a free manner this triangle angles¹ can be interpreted as an λ analogs of the φ based angles such as those of 36, 54 or 72 degrees.

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To Selena and her aesthetics

References

- [1] Turanyanin, D. N. The “Centrally Inscribed Square” Triangle, [The General Science Journal](https://www.gsjournal.net/Science-Journals/Research%20Papers/View/10153), (2025) <https://www.gsjournal.net/Science-Journals/Research%20Papers/View/10153>
- [2] [Golden ratio – Wikipedia](#),
- [3] Weisstein, Eric W. "Golden Ratio", From MathWorld-A Wolfram Web, <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/GoldenRatio.html>

¹ The base angle $\beta = (180 - \alpha)/2 = 61.46756^\circ$

Addendum

Before final closure of the themeⁱⁱ we would like to present briefly this interesting triangle of the kind. The related construction is here below

We left interested reader to reach the exact relation between side k of the inscribed regular 5-angle and radius r of circumscribed circle of this triangle. Our analysis however gives a quartic equation with fully irrational φ based coefficients. In case $k = 2$ one of the two real roots follows as negative $-\cot(36)$, i.e. -1.376381920 , and another is positive $r = 3.122787018\dots$. The related apex angle we finally get is

$$\alpha = 2\arctan(2.8031003/4.4991689) \approx 63.847979^\circ$$

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i Obvious first step, assuming $q = d/2$, is

$$\sqrt{r^2 - q^2}/(r + q) = q/r$$

ii The subject however stays open for further researching and generalizations.